

Aasis ELAN Transcription and Annotation Instructions (17.10.2024)

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Speech transcription instructions

Write what you hear the speaker say as raw text - that is, without capital letters and punctuation.

Errors are also written out. No phonetic transcription, plain text will do!

If needed, enter the following notes for the speech sample in the note file:

bad = bad signal quality (if the sound quality is so bad that you can't understand the speech, or if the sample has a bad echo)

empty = no content classified as speech in the sample

Transcription refinements and tags:

1. Short hesitations are transcribed as <hesitation> and one of the following alternatives, depending on which of them the hesitation most resembles: mm<hesitation>, hm<hesitation>, öm<hesitation>, öö<hesitation>, aa<hesitation>, ee<hesitation>, hmmm<hesitation>.
NOTE: choose the closest suitable option, e.g. even if the speaker pronounces "öööööö" for a long time, it is marked as two letters öö<hesitation>.
 - A "heureka"-style "aa" is transcribed without the <hesitation> tag.
2. Other paralinguistic units (if possible to identify):
 - Laughter transcribed as <laugh> in a separate cell. If there is laughter during the utterance, the <laugh> tag will be marked at the end of the speech cell. Quiet laughter is also transcribed with the <laugh> tag.
 - Backchannelling (supporting/giving feedback) during other speaker's turn: transcribed as <backch> and for example one of the following alternatives, depending on which of them the backchannelling most resembles: mm<backch>, joo<backch>, hmhm<backch>, nii<backch>, nojoo<backch>, okei<backch>, totta<backch>, vau<backch>, oho<backch> etc. Backchannelling is transcribed in a separate cell. Note! Most utterances that occur during the other speaker's turn are backchannelling. Backchannelling that occurs during the other speaker's laughter is not marked with the <backch> tag.
 - Other paralinguistic units, such as coughs, sighs, loud tongue clicks etc. are transcribed with <paral>
3. Words in the wrong language are transcribed <trans>, but if you recognize the language, e.g. English <transen> and Swedish <transsv> are transcribed. If you recognize other languages, add the corresponding combination of letters to the trans tag and mark which language it corresponds with in the excel notes file.
NOTE: names in foreign languages are not marked with <trans> but with <name>, see the instructions below!
 - Loanwords such as "cheatata" (engl: cheat) are transcribed as cheatata<transen>

4. Non-words and words that cannot be understood are transcribed <garbage>.
 - Only one <garbage> character is used in long, verbose "garbage".
NOTE: After <garbage> there may still be valid speech in the target language, don't leave transcription unfinished at <garbage>!
 - Try to transcribe without using this tag and rather transcribe the words as in section 5 if you can understand the speaker with small effort.
5. Almost correct words (based on the context) are marked between asterisks (*): e.g.
 - intended "muusikko", pronounced "musikko", marked *musikko*
 - intended "urheilija", pronounced "uhurelija", marked as *uhurelija*
 - intended "tämä", pronounced "tama", marked as *tama*
 - If a word is stretched, mark it with the asterisks as well. For example, a stretched "eli" is marked *eeeeli* (with as many e-letters as you feel appropriate for the length of the utterance).

-> Use discretion with "borderline cases": if, for example, the /ä/ sound falls somewhere between /a/ and /ä/ and does not interfere with the intelligibility of the word, it is not marked with *!
6. **NOTE:** forms that can be interpreted as colloquial are not counted as errors and are not marked with *, e.g.
 - meant "minä olen ollut", pronounced "mä oon ollu" or "moon ollu", marked "mä oon ollu"
 - meant "suvussasi", pronounced "suvussas", marked "suvussas"
7. Names are written in their original form if it is known (not as they are pronounced), and <name> is added after the name: e.g. aapo<name>, jyväskylä<name>, mallorca<name>. Add also names on companies etc. (e.g. previous work places) are transcribed with this <name> tag.
8. Foreign language names are also transcribed orthographically, but if you can't make out the name, just <name> is entered and an empty space is normally left in the adjacent words.
NOTE: However, do not use special characters like é, á, ž - replace them with regular e, etc.!
9. Correct words are transcribed as they are, regardless of the sentence's logic: e.g. "and I listening to him a lot", "every day I go sports every day", "ja minä kuuntele hänelle paljon", "joka päivä minä menen urheilu joka päivä"
10. Unfinished words (stuttering) are marked with a hyphen: e.g. "soccer and bad- badminton", "jalkapalloa ja sul- sulkapalloa". If there is a pause in the middle of a stutter, two "- " are marked at the cut-off points: "asiakas- " "-ta". If the speaker stutters and it is incorrect, mark it between two asterisks, for example "*viet-* veitsi".
11. If the speaker lists letters, these are transcribed as letters, for example a b c. The word "ok" is transcribed as "o k" (with a space in between the letters).

ELAN speech transcription and nonverbal features annotation instructions

Setup:

1. Open the ELAN program.
2. Download all the necessary video and audio files on your computer locally.
3. Open the cam3 video file and the ELAN template (File > New > choose the files).
4. Link the necessary files to the ELAN file: Edit > Linked files > Add > Apply
 - a. Link all the video and audio files for each exercise.
5. The following annotation tiers should be automatically created with the template:
 - a. Speaker1code_text, Speaker1code_hand, Speaker1code_head, Speaker1code_body, Speaker2code_text, Speaker2code_hand, Speaker2code_head, Speaker2code_body, Performance
 - b. Rename the annotation tiers by replacing the speaker codes with the correct speaker IDs. For example: Speaker092_text
6. Save the file, following this naming convention:
YYYYMMDD_speakerXXXspeakerXXX_taskX_transcriber, for example
20240819_speaker092speaker093_task5_nn

Segmentation: Segment the speech on the speaker1code_text and speaker2code_text tiers. If an utterance is long, you can cut a segment between words to make transcribing easier later.

1. In the performance tier, create a segment as long as the actual performance of the exercise (excluding anything extra, e.g. the researcher giving instructions). Do not transcribe or annotate anything outside of this segment.
2. Make the waveform visible (View > Waveform) so that you can use it as a help when segmenting speech.
3. Segment the speech in Segmentation mode (Options > Segmentation mode). Right click the correct tier to select it. Use the option “Two keystrokes per annotation – non-adjacent annotations”. Play the video and create segments by pressing enter. After segmenting the video once, check your segments and realign them if necessary.
 - a. Some useful shortcuts:
 - i. Ctrl + space = play/pause
 - ii. Shift + space = play selection
 - iii. Ctrl + B = go to beginning
 - iv. Ctrl + E = go to end
 - v. Ctrl + arrows = next or previous frame
 - vi. Shift + arrows = 1 second forward or back
 - vii. Ctrl + shift + arrows = 1 pixel forward or back
 - viii. Shift + enter = begin or end annotation box
 - ix. Ctrl + / = beginning or end of selection
4. Segment laughing (<laugh>) and backchanneling (<backch>) in their own cells.

Transcription: Transcribe the speech to text according to the instruction above (Speech transcription instructions) on the speaker1code_text and speaker2code_text tiers.

1. Transcribe the speech in Transcription mode (Options > Transcription mode).
 - a. Some useful shortcuts:
 - i. Replay the cell by pressing the tab key.
 - ii. Move to the next cell by pressing Enter.

Pauses: Create new annotation tiers for both speakers' pauses and link the “Pauses” tier type to the tiers. Annotate silent pauses.

1. Tier > Create Annotations from gaps > Choose speaker1code_text > Create annotation on a new tier, name it speaker1code_pauses > Value for the new annotation, Specific value: name <SP> > Ok. Then Tier > Change tier attributes > Tier type > Pause (and repeat this for the other speaker).
2. Annotating the silent pauses (SP):
 - a. Now all the pauses are annotated as <SP>, so the normal pauses must be changed to <pause>. Go through both speakers' pause tiers and change the tag by double-clicking on the pause segments. Silent pauses that occur during a speaker's turn are left as <SP>, and other pauses (such as pauses during the other speaker's turn or when both speakers are silent) are changed to <pause>. If it is difficult to define whether a pause is the speaker's "own" pause (<SP>) or not, then mark it with the <pause> tag.
 - b. Note down which files have been annotated with the <SP> tags in the excel notes file.

Overlapping speech: Create a new annotation tier from overlapping speech.

1. Tier > Create annotations from overlaps > Choose speaker1code_text and speakercode2_text > Regardless of their annotation values > Name the tier Speech_overlap > Choose specific value > Name it speech_overlap.

Annotating nonverbal features:

1. Hand & head & body features of a speaker will be annotated on their own tiers. Segment the feature and add a tag: click and drag to create the segment, then double-click on the annotation and choose a tag from the controlled vocabulary (see the table below).
 - 1.1. All features will be annotated as "blocks". For instance, if the speaker leans forwards and stays in this position for a while, this will be marked as "forward" for as long as they lean forwards and do not go back to their normal sitting position. So, the whole act of leaning forward is marked, and not, for example, only the active movement of leaning.
 - 1.2. Mark an estimation of how much eye contact each speaker had on a scale of 1-3 (1: little, 2: normal, 3: a lot) in the notes excel.

Tier	Tags
head movement (head)	nodding (nod) shaking the head (shake) other, for example tilting the head (head_other)
hand movement (hand)	gesturing (gesture) pointing (point) fidgeting (fidget)
body movement (body)	leaning forward (forward) leaning backward (back) other, for example swaying (body_other)
gaze (gaze)	looking at the interlocutor (interlocutor) looking at the material (material) looking away (away) eyes closed (blink)

Remember to save the file often!

Output: Create an output .csv file.

1. In ELAN: Search > Find (and Replace) > Tier = All, write .* in the search box and check “regular expression” > Press Search > Query > Export > Tab-delimited text > Save as date_speakerXXXspeakerXXX_taskX_transcriber_outputDate. (The file will be saved as a .txt file.)
2. In Excel: Data > From text/csv > Transform data > Delete Column 1 > Close & Load > Name the columns: Tier name, Start, Start_s, End, End_s, Duration, Duration_s, Label > Save as Date_speakerXXXspeakerXXX_taskX_annotoija_outputDate. (The file will be saved as a .csv file.)
3. Move the .eaf files and .csv output files to the allocated folder in the project’s group storage.